

3D Sand Printing for Steel Casting - A Game Changer

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Abstract

Additive Manufacturing (AM) has an increasing impact on modern fabrication processes. Especially in terms of tools, gauges and other consumables like grippers and fixtures, AM proves to decrease costs and speeds up development processes. In addition to metal AM processes 3D sand printing (3DSP) fills the gap towards larger parts with several tons of weight for example tooling frames for presses. With the need of a reduction of the CO₂ footprint of products and processes 3DSP allows to design more complex castings by using bionic principles. 3DSP enables more lightweight designs for castings than classical approaches, which leads to new ways of thinking tools and big parts for mobility applications. Especially in the transportation sector it opens new, cost-effective ways to manufacture big parts for trains and other heavy vehicles.

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1 Introduction

Sand casting as a manual manufacturing process has been established to form objects out of metals for more than 5 millennia. It provides a wide range of dimensions, complexity, and designs. Future growth of this “old” industry requires the application of the latest advances in mold production to keep up with market needs and competing technologies.

The potentials of 3D printing or additive manufacturing (AM) in general for casting were identified early [1]. Alas, the application has been limited mainly to prototyping. 3D sand printing for the fabrication of molds for steel and metal casting is based on the binder jetting process [2]. The single steps of this process are based on the selective application of a liquid binder by an inkjet system to a thin layer of powder i.e., silica sand to print a complex geometry mold as seen in figure 1. This process enables a pattern free direct mold production directly from CAD models.

Figure 1: Principle of binder jetting according to [3]

Often the term indirect additive manufacturing is used in this context, as the printed molds are used as tools for shaping i.e. pouring the final part. Through the integration of this technology in the existing casting lines in metal and steel foundries the following benefits for castings manufactured out of these printed molds are:

- Enabling a higher freedom of geometry [4-6]
- Possibility of new designs using bionic principles [4, 7]
- Lead time reduction through reduction or even substitution of process steps such as pattern making or machining [5, 8]
- Reduction of material consumption due reduction of weight [8-9]
- Better dimension control by reducing the number of molds and cores [5]
- Complex castings without tooling lead to a reduction of hard tooling requirements. [5, 8]
- Significant potential of reduction of CO₂ emissions compared to the traditional casting process due to design optimization and less material input and energy consumption [9]
- Reduction of the number of toxic consumables in sand mold manufacturing and environmental friendlier emissions compared to the conventional casting process [5]
- New opportunities for integrated sensors in molds [11-12]
- Cost reduction as a sum of all above

One of the main goals of this study was to apply bionic principles to develop more lightweight products by using casting technologies. Casting steel products in different sizes form a few kg to several tons by using printed molds and cores and even identify the possibility to combine it with other AM technologies is our main motivation.

2 Experimental methods

To prove the potential of bionic designs for existing parts out of steel casting, two representative examples are shown: one out of the mobility industry, a spare part for trains, the other one out of the automotive tooling industry, a bottom press housing.

2.1 Case Study Cargo Hinge

A cargo hinge is widely used a spare part in trains with a total weight of 635 g.

Figure 2: Boundary Conditions – Geometry & Material

Figure 3: Topology optimization results

First boundary conditions were set for the original design. The design and non-design space was set to a max. deflection of 0.25 mm. In addition, three different load case scenarios, a setting material parameter to EN 1.6220, G20Mn5, $E = 210 \text{ GPa}$, $\rho = 7,8 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\nu = 0,3$, $Rp0,2 = 300 \text{ MPa}$, were defined for the simulations using a commercial software tool (Altair® Inspire™, 2020.1.1) for bionic design. The goal was to achieve a reduction of weight around 20% without losing any functionality.

Finally, before going into casting simulation, a full FE analysis for all stresses in all three load case scenarios was carried out (figure 4). All the load cases had to reach our goal of a deflection of less than 0.25 mm.

Figure 4: FE analysis for the three set load cases scenarios

After verification of the load cases the engineering of the printed mold started. The riser and gating system were calculated, using a commercially available casting simulation program (Altair® Inspire™ Cast, 2021.1.2). Further the behavior of the metal filling and solidification were simulated (figure 5).

The position and dimension of riser and gating system were optimized to avoid porosity and other shrinkage related defects in several iterative steps.

Figure 5: Casting with riser and gating system (a), solidification simulation for porosity (b) and microporosity (c) after end of solidification

The resulting file of the mold was transferred to a 3D sand printer via .stl-format and printed according principles described earlier. After cleaning the mold (3 parts) were assembled and prepared for pouring by a zirconia wash. Then the part was finally formed by pouring liquid metal with $1590 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ into the mold, shaking out the residual (sand) and a cleaning step. After this the part was heat treated (normalizing at $920 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

2.2 Case Study Bottom Housing

In automotive industries, time is of the essence in product development. This has been true for a long time, but in the last years the reduction of CO_2 during the manufacturing process gets more and more important. Using the same methods a bottom housing, made from EN 1.1118, G24Mn6, for a press in automotive industry was designed according to the principle of reduced stresses optimization for weight reduction.

Figure 7: CAD file of bionic optimized sand mold for bottom housing

The final size of the bottom housing was 2.840 x 650 x 2.100 mm and 6.7 t in weight compared to the original part with 8 t.

3 Results

It was shown that a cargo hinge optimized with respect to bionic principles can be cast using 3DSP. Also the goal of a weight reduction of 20 %, without losing any functionality as seen in figure 8 has been reached.

Figure 8: CAD file of bionic optimized mold for bottom housing

The results of the smaller casting part in this study could be upscaled to the finished bottom house casting. A reduction of approximately 15% of weight in comparison to the original used part could be achieved, too.

Figure 9: CAD file of bionic optimized mold for bottom housing

4 Summary

As shown above 3DSP has become an important, even disruptive tool in the steel casting industry. It's main applications are for complex parts. It enables casts for small, complex, and heavy parts as well. It offers new design opportunities like bionic design and will even allow for multipart casts in metal. It provides a smart way to save weight and it lowers the CO₂ consumption during the production process through the option of near net shape casting and reduces manufacturing time.

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